

THE PRINCIPAL'S PERCEPTION ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DISASTER PREPAREDNESS SCHOOL

ZUHRIANA K. YUSUF¹, ABDUL HARIS PANAI², HASIM³ and

MUHAMMAD ISMAN JUSUF⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Pascasarjana, Universitas Negeri Gorontalo, Indonesia.

Abstract

This study aims to determine school principals' perceptions on the implementation of Disaster Preparedness Schools, especially in Bone Bolango District. Data were collected using observation, documentation, and questionnaire distribution. The data were then analyzed using descriptive statistical analysis techniques. The results showed that most school principals' perceptions of the knowledge and skills, along with the policies in the implementation of Disaster Preparedness Schools were good. In terms of knowledge and skills, 63.7% of principals have a good perception, while the other 36.3% have a sufficient perception. In terms of policy, 87.3% of principals have a good perception and 12.7% have a moderate perception. On the other hand, principals' perceptions in terms of emergency response and resource mobilization are lacking, where, in terms of emergency response, only 28.4% of principals have a good perception, while the other 71.6% have a moderate perception. In terms of resource mobilization, 20.6% of principals have a good perception and 79.4% have a moderate perception. Thus, improvements and enhancements need to be made to both parameters.

Keywords: Policy Implementation, Descriptive Research, Disaster Preparedness School.

INTRODUCTION

Natural disasters are one of the natural phenomena that threaten the sustainability of human life. The negative impacts can be in the form of material and non-material losses. Disasters that occur due to environmental and human influences can be exemplified such as floods, landslides, fires, work accidents, technological failures, social conflicts between groups, and terror. Natural disasters that occur naturally include earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, long droughts, and hurricanes (Law No. 24/2007).

Natural disasters can happen anytime, anywhere, and to anyone, so disaster preparedness education should ideally be provided to all levels of society, including early childhood through children's education programs. In this case, disaster knowledge is given to elementary school students, community schools, and also communities around schools because school-age children are very vulnerable to natural disasters. This is anticipated with disaster education so that they are better prepared to face disasters (Boon & Pagilano, 2015).

In the research of Seddighi, *et al.* (2021), one way to reduce children's vulnerability to disaster threats is to learn about natural disaster hazards and reduce disaster risk at school. Thus, this knowledge will be able to help children build skills and contribute to disaster risk management, as well as develop attitudes and dispositions to work collectively when their families and communities are threatened or affected by disasters.

Various efforts have been made to reduce disaster risk. One of them is the creation of Law No. 24/2007 on Disaster Management. According to the law, disaster risk reduction efforts must be incorporated into development programs, including in the field of education. Education is one of the determining factors in disaster risk reduction activities.

Disaster preparedness in schools is a joint effort and responsibility of the school community and school stakeholders. School members are all people who are present and involved in teaching and learning activities, namely students, teachers, education personnel, and principals. School stakeholders are all components of the community with an interest in the school, both community members and surrounding community institutions. To measure the efforts made by schools in building a Disaster Preparedness School (SSB), it is necessary to set several parameters, including

- 1) Attitudes and actions,
- 2) School policies,
- 3) Preparedness Planning,
- 4) Resource Mobilization (Disaster Education Consortium, 2011).

Based on this description, the author is interested in conducting a study entitled "**The Principals' Perceptions on the Implementation of Disaster Preparedness Schools**". The objective to be achieved in this study is to determine the perceptions of school principals about the implementation of Disaster Preparedness Schools, especially in Bone Bolango District.

METHODS

This research was conducted in schools throughout the Bone Bolango Regency. The sample in this study was 102 school principals in Bone Bolango Regency who were determined through the total sampling method. Data collection was carried out using various instruments, such as observation, documentation, and questionnaire distribution. The existing research data was then analyzed using descriptive statistical analysis techniques.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Principals' Perceptions of the Implementation of Disaster Preparedness Schools in Bone Bolango District

Principals' perceptions were assessed based on four parameters, namely perceptions about knowledge and skills in SSB implementation, perceptions about policies in SSB implementation, perceptions about emergency response in SSB implementation, and perceptions about resource mobilization. The results of the assessment are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Respondents Based on Principal Perception

Parameters	Good Perception		Fair Perception	
	n	%	n	%
Principals' perceptions of knowledge and skills in implementing Disaster Preparedness School	65	63,7	37	36,3
Principals' perceptions of policies in the implementation of Disaster Preparedness School	89	87,3	13	12,7
Principals' perceptions of emergency response in the implementation of Disaster Preparedness School	29	28,4	73	71,6
Principals' perceptions of resource mobilization in the implementation of Disaster Preparedness School	21	20,6	81	79,4

Source: primary data, 2023

Discussion

Based on the data in Table 1, some principals have already gained knowledge and skills in disaster preparedness and management. A total of 65 principals have a good perception, while 37 others have a moderate perception. Based on the research data, it can be said that some principals already know about disaster preparedness and handling, have increased knowledge and skills of preparedness in extracurricular activities, and there are even schools that provide materials and materials related to disaster preparedness.

In practice, so far, Indonesia is a disaster-prone country, but anti-disaster education or Disaster Preparedness School (SSB) has not been optimal so once a disaster occurs it always takes many victims. This is due to negligence and the habit of taking problems lightly. Therefore, efforts to improve SSB are absolutely necessary if we do not want to experience the same thing in the future.

Disaster preparedness is in the interest of all individuals and all institutions, including educational institutions. Schools can provide practical guidance in disaster management, both before, during, and after a disaster. In Indonesia itself, school readiness to deal with disasters is still considered lacking. Schools that are ready and alert in the face of disasters have the following criteria:

1. Have knowledge in facing and coping with disasters
2. Emergency response plan in place
3. Early warning system in place
4. Policies and guidelines on disaster management
5. Resource mobilization in schools.

Conversely, unprepared and alert schools are characterized by the absence of disaster preparedness training, early warning systems, emergency response plans, and regulations or policies related to disaster management. Therefore, the government through Regulation of the Head of the National Disaster Management Agency No. 04/2012 regulates the Implementation of Safe Schools/Madrasahs from Disasters.

In addition, the Ministry of National Education in 2008 published the Curriculum Development of Special Service Education for Non-Formal Education Package A for Natural Disaster Areas (BNPB, 2012). In shaping this preparedness, students as one of the components that have the largest proportion also need to play an active and participatory role in disaster preparedness efforts at the school level.

Based on the data in Table 1, it is known that around 89 principals have a good perception of policies related to the implementation of SSB, while 13 others have a moderate perception. The research found that some schools have provided educational policies/programs related to natural disaster preparedness. Some teachers and staff already know Permendikbud No. 33 of 2019 concerning the Implementation of Disaster-Safe Education Unit Programs, and some have even made policies/programs regarding the implementation of disaster-safe education unit programs.

Policies and guidelines are concrete efforts to implement disaster preparedness activities. The necessary policies are public education policies, emergency response plans, disaster warning systems, and resource mobilization, including funding, management organizations, human resources, and essential facilities for disaster emergencies. Policies can be realized in various forms but will be more meaningful if they are concretely included in regulations, such as decrees or regional regulations accompanied by clear job descriptions.

Based on the research data displayed in Table 1, it is known that there are around 29 teachers who have a good perception regarding emergency response in the implementation of SSB, while 73 others have a sufficient perception. This is in accordance with the findings of the researchers, where the equipment to convey/disseminate warnings, such as bells, sirens, and so on, is still lacking. In addition, not all school principals issued decrees for the disaster preparedness groups, and not all of them carried out activities in accordance with their main tasks and functions.

The incident changed the paradigm of disaster management from emergency response to prevention and disaster risk reduction (DRR). Emergency response is a series of activities carried out immediately after a disaster. However, the results of this study found that the attitude of emergency response to disasters is still very lacking, so the dissemination of warnings to government institutions, institutions, and communities in risk areas is also very lacking. This results in actions not being taken quickly in the event of a disaster, either in terms of evacuating or saving property/assets or preventing further damage.

Sudden emergencies are characterized by overwhelming needs. Priorities compete for immediate attention. Transportation and communication infrastructure is lost or damaged, humanitarian aid is slow to arrive, and citizen assistance is abundant but unorganized, local government institutions are paralyzed because they are unprepared for the demands of the job. In this situation, visions of chaos immediately arise.

Lack of coordination is characterized by several things, including gaps in services to disaster-affected communities, duplication of efforts/programs, inappropriate or unevenly and quickly distributed assistance, inefficient use of resources, confusion of information, slow response to

changing conditions, and frustration at the level of relief organizations, officials, and survivors on various matters related to assistance.

Based on the research data, it was found that around 21 principals had a good perception of resource mobilization, while 81 others had a moderate perception. This indicates that some teachers and students only know the disaster preparedness policy but not the simulation, thus magnifying the impact of disasters and not having the vigilance and anticipation of handling disasters early on. This happens because many schools do not have a fixed procedure (PROTAP) on evacuation in the event of a disaster. Knowledge and learning about disaster risk reduction should be provided to all levels of society, including children in schools. Learning will be more effective if it is packaged in the form of training and the delivery is assisted by using a module containing fixed procedures.

In line with the Hyogo Framework for Action 2005-2015, a way to strengthen disaster preparedness to accelerate effective response at all levels of society is through education or training. The Hyogo Framework prioritizes three things, namely using knowledge, innovation, and education to build a culture of safety and resilience at all levels. Disaster preparedness is closely related to a person's *self-efficacy*.

Early Warning Systems at the community level should be promoted jointly between the public sector (local government), stakeholders working and representing communities, and traditional structures. Therefore, local governments should involve community leaders to ensure that the Banjar system (customary system) supports and provides input on natural disaster hazards, disaster preparedness, and early warning.

If the schemes, procedures, and content of warning messages are well understood by all parties, the information from the early warning system will help local decision-makers and at-risk communities make better (and faster) decisions.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results that have been presented, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Principals' perceptions of knowledge and skills in implementing disaster preparedness schools were 65 people (63.7%) with good perceptions while 37 people (36.3%) had moderate perceptions.
2. Principals' perceptions of policies in implementing disaster preparedness schools were 89 people (87.3%) with good perceptions while 13 people (12.7%) had moderate perceptions.
3. Principals' perceptions of emergency response in implementing disaster preparedness schools were 73 people (71.6%) with moderate perceptions while 29 people (28.4%) had good perceptions.
4. Principals' perceptions of resource mobilization in implementing disaster preparedness schools were 81 people (79.4%) with moderate perceptions while 21 people (20.6%) had good perceptions.

Reference

- 1) "Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 24 Tahun 2007 tentang Penanggulangan Bencana," 2017.
- 2) Asian Disaster reduction Center. (2011). *Parameter Kesiapsiagaan Sekolah*. Jakarta: Konsorsium Pendidikan Bencana Indonesia.
- 3) Asian Disaster reduction Center. (2011). *Sekolah Siaga Bencana*. Jakarta: Konsorsium Pendidikan Bencana Indonesia.
- 4) BNPB. (2009). *National Disaster Management Plan*. Jakarta. BNPB
- 5) Boon, Brown & Pagliano. (2014). Emergency planning for students with disabilities: a survey of Australian schools. *Australian Journal of Emergency Management I* Volume 29, No. 1, January 2014.
- 6) Erly Zohrian, Sigit Santosa, Sarwono. (2015). Pengaruh Model Pembelajaran Terpadu Pada Pengintegrasian Materi Pengurangan Risiko Bencana Dalam Mata Pelajaran IPS SMP Terhadap Pengetahuan dan Kesiapsiagaan Bencana. *Jurnal GeoEco*, 1(2), Hlm. 170-179.
- 7) Gempa bumi Merusak di Yogyakarta 27 Mei 2006. <http://www.bmg.go.id/>. KPB. 2011. *Kerangka Kerja Sekolah Siaga Bencana disusun bersama oleh : Konsursium Pendidikan Bencana*.
- 8) Konsorsium Pendidikan Bencana. *Kerangka Kerja Sekolah Siaga Bencana*. Jakarta : Konsorsium Pendidikan Bencana, 2011.
- 9) Lindung Siswanto. (2012). Sistem Informasi Manajemen Komando Tanggap Darurat Bencana Letusan Gunung Merapi. *Jurnal Teknologi Informasi*, VII(19), Hlm 15-24.
- 10) Nirmalawati. (2011). Pembentukan Konsep Diri Pada Siswa Pendidikan Dasar Dalam Memahami Mitigasi Bencana. *Jurnal Smartek*, 9(1), Hlm. 61-69.
- 11) Nur Aisyah dan Dwi Indah. (2012). Tinjauan Dampak Banjir Lahar Kali Putih, Kabupaten Magelang Pasca Erupsi Merapi 2010. *Jurnal Teknologi Technoscientia*, 5(1), Hlm. 19-30.
- 12) Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 21 Tahun 2008 Tentang Penyelenggaraan Penanggulangan Bencana.
- 13) Perry, RW and MK Lindell. (2008). Volcanic Risk Perception and Adjustment in Multi Hazard Environment. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 172, Hlm. 170-178.
- 14) Prakoso, B., Widana, I. D. K. K., & Subiyanto, A. (2021). Pendidikan Dan Literasi Bencana Dalam Kerangka Tri Sentra Pendidikan Untuk Generasi Tangguh Bencana Disaster. *Jurnal Manajemen Bencana*, 7(1), 59–76. <https://doi.org/10.33172/jmb.v7i1.705>
- 15) Ramli, S. (2010). *Manajemen Bencana*. Jakarta. Dian Rakyat.
- 16) Sugiyono. 2012. *Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 17) Suharsimi Arikunto. 2006. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- 18) Surono, P. Jousset, J. Pallister, M.Boichu, M.F Buongiorno, A. Budisantoso, F. Costa, S. Andreastuti, F. Prats, D. Scheiner, L. Clarisse, H. Humaida, S. Sumarti, C. Bignami, J. Griswold, S. Carn, C. Oppenheimer, and F. Lavigne. (2012). The 2010 Explosive Eruption of Java's Merapi Volcano a '100-year' Event. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 241-242, Hlm. 121-135.
- 19) Sutton, J and K. Tierney. (2006). *Disaster Preparedness: Concepts, Guidance and Reserach. The Fritz Institute: San Fransisco*.
- 20) Wood, N and C. Soulard. (2009). Variation in Population Exposure and Sensivity to Lahar Hazard from Mount Rainer, Washington. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 188, Hlm. 367-378.